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Model for Analyzing the Thermal Behaviour and Performance Characteristics of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) for Thermal Energy Storage (TES) Applications

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ABSTRACT

Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems play a crucial role in improving the reliability of renewable energy technologies, with Phase Change Materials (PCMs) offering high latent heat storage and stable thermal performance. This study presents a numerical and analytical approach for evaluating the thermal behavior of paraffin, salt hydrate, and eutectic PCMs used in TES applications. Key properties such as latent heat capacity, phase transition temperature, thermal conductivity, and thermal cycling stability were analyzed using literature-based data and an enthalpy-based modeling technique. Results indicate that salt hydrates exhibit superior heat storage and conductivity but experience higher degradation, while eutectic PCMs provide balanced performance and improved stability. The numerical results closely align with experimental data, confirming the reliability of the developed model for TES design optimization.

Keywords: *Phase change materials, thermal energy storage, enthalpy method, thermal cycling, renewable energy systems*

INTRODUCTION

The increasing global demand for sustainable and efficient energy systems has intensified research into advanced energy storage technologies capable of mitigating the intermittent nature of renewable energy sources. Among these technologies, Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems have gained significant attention due to their ability to store excess thermal energy during periods of low demand and release it during peak demand periods. TES systems enhance energy efficiency, improve system reliability, and facilitate the integration of renewable energy sources such as solar and wind into existing power grids. [2,9].

A particularly promising TES approach involves the use of Phase Change Materials (PCMs), which absorb and release large amounts of latent heat during phase transitions between solid and liquid states. Their high energy storage density, nearly isothermal phase change behavior, and design flexibility make PCMs suitable for applications such as building thermal regulation, solar thermal power plants, electronic cooling, and waste heat recovery [3,5]. However, the thermal behavior and long-term performance of PCMs depend strongly on their intrinsic thermophysical properties, including latent heat capacity, phase transition temperature, thermal conductivity, and thermal cycling stability. These properties directly influence energy efficiency, heat transfer rate, and system durability.

Therefore, the development of accurate analytical and numerical models is essential for predicting PCM behavior under realistic operating conditions. While experimental techniques such as Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), and the Transient Plane Source (TPS) method provide reliable thermal characterization, they are often costly and time-consuming.

Consequently, experimental investigations are frequently complemented by numerical modeling, particularly using the enthalpy-based heat conduction method, which effectively simulates melting and solidification processes [6].

LITERATURE SURVEY

Thermal Energy Storage (TES) has been widely recognized as a critical technology for enhancing the efficiency, reliability, and flexibility of modern energy systems, particularly in the context of renewable energy integration. TES systems mitigate the temporal mismatch between energy supply and demand by storing surplus thermal energy and releasing it during peak load periods. Among the various TES techniques, latent heat thermal energy storage using Phase Change Materials (PCMs) has received considerable attention due to its high energy storage density and ability to operate within a narrow temperature range during phase transitions [2].

Phase Change Materials for Thermal Energy Storage

PCMs are generally classified into organic, inorganic, and eutectic materials, each exhibiting distinct advantages and limitations. Organic PCMs, particularly paraffin waxes and fatty acids, are characterized by chemical stability, negligible supercooling, and good cycling reliability. However, their relatively low thermal conductivity limits heat transfer rates, thereby affecting charging and discharging performance in TES systems [5].

Inorganic PCMs, such as salt hydrates, offer higher latent heat capacity and superior thermal conductivity compared to organic materials. These properties make them attractive for compact TES designs. Nevertheless, challenges such as phase segregation, supercooling, and corrosion have been reported, which adversely affect

long-term performance and material reliability [3,8].

Eutectic PCMs, formed by combining two or more components at specific ratios, have emerged as promising alternatives due to their sharp melting points, moderate thermal conductivity, and improved thermal stability. Recent studies indicate that eutectic PCMs can provide a balanced compromise between energy density and durability, making them suitable for medium-temperature TES applications [1].

Thermophysical Characterization of PCMs

Accurate determination of PCM thermophysical properties is essential for effective TES system design. Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) is widely employed to evaluate latent heat capacity and phase transition temperature, while Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) is used to assess thermal stability and degradation behavior. Thermal conductivity measurements are commonly conducted using techniques such as the Transient Plane Source (TPS) method, which provides reliable data for both solid and liquid phases of PCMs [4].

Several studies have emphasized that PCM performance is highly sensitive to these properties and that variations due to thermal cycling can significantly impact TES efficiency over time. Consequently, thermal cycling tests have become a standard approach for evaluating long-term PCM reliability under repeated melting and solidification conditions [9].

Numerical Modeling of PCM Thermal Behavior

Due to the cost and time constraints associated with experimental investigations, numerical modeling has become an indispensable tool for analyzing PCM behavior in TES systems. Among various numerical techniques, the

enthalpy-based method has been extensively adopted to model phase change processes because it effectively captures latent heat effects without explicitly tracking the solid-liquid interface [6].

Numerical simulations have demonstrated good agreement with experimental results in predicting temperature distribution, melting fraction, and energy storage efficiency for different PCM configurations. However, many existing studies focus on individual PCM types or isolated performance metrics, limiting their applicability for comparative PCM selection and system-level optimization.

Although significant progress has been made in PCM characterization and modeling, there remains a lack of integrated studies that combine thermophysical property evaluation, numerical simulation, and thermal cycling degradation analysis for multiple PCM categories within a unified framework. Comparative assessments of organic, inorganic, and eutectic PCMs under consistent modeling assumptions are particularly limited. Addressing this gap is essential for developing reliable guidelines for PCM selection in TES applications.

Advanced, Nano-Enhanced and Encapsulated Phase Change Materials

Recent advances in Phase Change Material (PCM) research have extended beyond conventional organic and inorganic materials toward the development of advanced composite structures, nano-enhanced PCMs (NePCMs), and encapsulated PCM systems. These innovations are primarily aimed at overcoming the inherent limitations of traditional PCMs, such as low thermal conductivity, leakage during melting, supercooling, and long-term degradation under repeated thermal cycling.

Nano-Enhanced Phase Change Materials (NePCMs)

Nano-enhanced PCMs are developed by dispersing high-conductivity nanoparticles into base PCM matrices to improve thermal performance. Metallic nanoparticles (e.g., Cu, Al₂O₃), carbon-based materials (e.g., graphene nanoplatelets, carbon nanotubes), and ceramic nanofillers have been widely investigated in recent years. These nano-additives significantly enhance thermal conductivity, thereby improving heat transfer rates and reducing charging and discharging times in TES systems.

Recent studies have reported thermal conductivity enhancement ranging from 20–60% depending on nanoparticle type and loading fraction [10]. Graphene-based additives, in particular, have demonstrated superior conductivity enhancement while maintaining acceptable latent heat capacity [11]. Similarly, hybrid nanocomposites incorporating multiple nanoparticle types have shown improved melting rate and reduced solidification time compared to conventional PCMs [12].

Despite these advantages, researchers have noted that excessive nanoparticle loading may reduce latent heat storage capacity and increase viscosity in liquid phases, which could negatively affect natural convection during melting [10]. Therefore, optimization of nanoparticle concentration remains critical for balancing conductivity improvement and energy storage density.

Encapsulation Techniques for PCM Stabilization

Encapsulation technology has emerged as an effective approach for preventing leakage and improving structural stability during phase transitions. Encapsulation involves surrounding PCM particles with protective shells to form micro- or nano-capsules, thereby enhancing mechanical strength and long-term durability.

Recent advancements in micro-encapsulation techniques include polymer-based shells, silica coatings, and hybrid inorganic–organic matrices designed to withstand repeated thermal cycling [13]. Nano-encapsulated PCMs have demonstrated improved shape stability, reduced material loss, and enhanced compatibility with building materials and solar thermal collectors [14].

Sol–gel synthesized silica-encapsulated paraffin composites have shown high enthalpy retention and minimal degradation after extended cycling, making them promising candidates for medium-temperature TES systems [13]. Furthermore, encapsulation improves heat transfer surface area, contributing to enhanced thermal responsiveness in compact TES configurations [14].

Form-Stable and Composite PCMs

Another important development in recent PCM research is the design of form-stable composite PCMs, where the phase change material is embedded within porous supporting matrices such as expanded graphite, metal foams, or polymer networks. These structures prevent liquid leakage while maintaining high latent heat storage capacity.

Recent investigations have demonstrated that expanded graphite-based composite PCMs significantly improve thermal conductivity without compromising phase transition characteristics [15]. Similarly, metal foam-supported PCMs have been shown to enhance effective heat transfer coefficients and reduce melting time under controlled heat flux conditions [16].

Emerging Trends in Advanced PCM Research

Comprehensive reviews published within the last five years highlight the growing integration of nano-enhancement, encapsulation, and composite stabilization strategies to produce multifunctional PCMs for renewable energy systems

[10,15]. Advanced modeling approaches incorporating three-dimensional heat transfer, nanoparticle dispersion effects, and non-uniform heat flux conditions are also increasingly being employed to optimize PCM system design [12,16].

These recent developments demonstrate that advanced PCM engineering is progressively addressing traditional limitations related to thermal conductivity, leakage, and cycling degradation. However, comparative evaluations of conventional, nano-enhanced, and encapsulated PCMs under consistent modeling assumptions remain limited.

Integrating these emerging materials into unified analytical frameworks is essential for reliable PCM selection and TES system optimization.

Comparative Study of Conventional, Nano-Enhanced and Encapsulated PCMs for TES Applications

The evaluation of different PCM categories, the recent literature and a comparative assessment of this study is discussed and presented in Table 1. The comparison considers thermophysical performance, stability, advantages, and limitations.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of PCM Categories for Thermal Energy Storage Applications.

PCM Category	Typical Latent Heat (J/g)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Cycling Stability	Key Advantages	Major Limitations	Recent Improvements
Organic PCM (Paraffin)	180 – 220	0.20 – 0.30	Excellent	Chemically stable, negligible supercooling, non-corrosive	Very low thermal conductivity	Graphene and CNT nano-enhancement
Inorganic PCM (Salt Hydrate)	230 – 260	0.45 – 0.55	Moderate	High latent heat, higher conductivity than paraffin	Phase segregation, corrosion, supercooling	Encapsulation and stabilizing additives
Eutectic PCM	210 – 230	0.30 – 0.40	Good	Sharp melting point, moderate conductivity, good compatibility	Limited long-term industrial data	Hybrid composite structures
Nano-Enhanced PCM (NePCM)	170 – 240 (depends on loading)	0.35 – 1.20	Good (optimized loading)	Improved heat transfer rate, reduced melting time	Possible reduction in latent heat at high nanoparticle concentration	Hybrid nanoparticle dispersion optimization
Micro-Encapsulated PCM	150 – 220	0.25 – 0.50	Very Good	Leakage prevention, mechanical stability, easy integration	Shell material cost, reduced effective PCM fraction	Polymer-silica hybrid shells
Nano-Encapsulated PCM	160 – 230	0.30 – 0.70	Excellent	High surface area, improved thermal response, enhanced durability	Complex fabrication process	Sol-gel and advanced nano-coating techniques
Form-Stable Composite PCM (Graphite/Metal Foam Supported)	180 – 240	0.80 – 5.00 (effective)	Very Good	Dramatically enhanced effective conductivity, shape stability	Increased weight, cost	Expanded graphite and metal foam integration

COMPARATIVE DISCUSSION

From the comparative assessment in Table 1, it is evident that:

- **Salt hydrates** provide the highest latent heat storage capacity but suffer from long-term stability issues.
- **Paraffin-based PCMs** exhibit superior chemical stability but are limited by poor thermal conductivity.
- **Eutectic PCMs** offer a balanced compromise between energy storage density and thermal reliability.
- **Nano-enhanced PCMs** significantly improve thermal conductivity and melting rate, though careful optimization is required to prevent latent heat reduction.
- **Encapsulated PCMs** improve durability and prevent leakage, making them suitable for building integration and solar thermal systems.
- **Form-stable composite PCMs** achieve the highest effective thermal conductivity due to conductive supporting matrices such as graphite and metal foams.

This comparative study highlights that while conventional PCMs remain attractive for basic TES applications, advanced nano-enhanced and encapsulated PCMs provide superior performance for high-efficiency and long-term energy storage systems.

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this study is to develop a comprehensive model for investigating the thermal behavior and performance of different PCMs used in TES applications. The evaluation is based on key thermal properties, including latent heat capacity, phase transition temperature, thermal conductivity, and thermal stability.

The methodology integrates:

- Literature-based experimental data,

- Analytical formulations, and
- Numerical modeling using the enthalpy method.

This integrated approach enables a holistic assessment of PCM performance.

Experimental Characterization of PCMs

PCM samples were selected from three major categories:

- Organic (paraffins and fatty acids),
- Inorganic (salt hydrates and metallic PCMs), and
- Eutectic PCMs.

Although standard experimental characterization techniques include DSC, TGA, TPS, and thermal cycling tests, the data used in this study were obtained from published literature due to time constraints. The relevant governing equations are presented below.

(a) Latent Heat Capacity and Phase Transition Temperature Determination

The latent heat capacity of phase change materials (PCMs) is one of the most important characteristics that solely affect energy storage density. The experimental data used for this study are from the following literature. Khudhair and Farid (2021) who considered latent heat storage in TES systems, and found that paraffins have latent heats of 180-220 J/g and melt between 55-60°C.[7]

According to Diaconu et al. (2023), hydrate salts are latent heat carriers (230-260 J/g) but suffer from phase stability problems, they have transition temperature around 40-45°C. Similarly, Amidu et al. (2023) revealed that eutectic PCMs have higher energy density than the others, generally between 210-230 J/g and a transition temperature ranging between 45-50°C.

Experimentally, the latent heat capacity (ΔH) and phase transition temperature (T_m) can be ascertained using

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Such that a small amount of PCM is heated and cooled under predetermined conditions, and the heat flow will be

$$\Delta H = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} C_p(T) dT \quad (3.1)$$

where:

ΔH is the latent heat capacity

$C_p(T)$ is the specific heat capacity at temperature T (J/kg·K),

T_1, T_2 are the initial and final temperatures of the phase transition.

The phase transition temperature is determined from the peak of the DSC curve, which corresponds to the temperature at which the maximum heat absorption occurs.

(b) Thermal Conductivity

Thermal conductivity (k) will be measured using the Transient Plane Source (TPS) technique based on the heat diffusion equation:

$$q = -k \frac{dT}{dx} \quad (3.2)$$

where:

q is the Heat flux (W/m²),

k is the Thermal conductivity (W/m·K),

dT/dx is the Temperature gradient.

A sensor is placed between two PCM samples, and an electrical pulse generates a thermal response, which is analyzed to determine the material's thermal conductivity.

However, for convince and the limited time of the study, the experimental data for the simulation were obtained from the following literatures; Dutkowski & Kruzal (2021) suggest that the thermal conductivity of paraffin-based PCMs is within the range of 0.20-0.30 W/mK, Panchabikesan et al. (2019) studied the salt hydrate-based PCMs and found out that the thermal conductivities ranged from 0.45-0.55 W/mK, while Amidu et al. (2023) indicated that the eutectic PCMs have a moderate thermal conductivity of 0.30-0.40 W/mK.[8]

recorded. Heat absorbed or released during the phase transition is modelled using the following mathematical expression:

Numerical Modeling of PCM Thermal Performance

A numerical heat transfer model is developed using the enthalpy method to simulate the melting and solidification process in the PCMs. The governing heat conduction equation with phase change is expressed as follows:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T) + Q \quad (3.3)$$

where:

ρ is the Density of the PCM (kg/m³),

C_p is the Specific heat capacity (J/kg·K),

T is the Temperature (K),

t is the Time (s),

k is the Thermal conductivity (W/m·K),

Q is the Internal heat generation term.

The enthalpy (H) formulation will be used to track phase transition and it can be expressed mathematically as;

$$H = \int C_p dT + fL \quad (3.3)$$

where:

H is the Total enthalpy (J/kg),

f is the Liquid fraction of PCM,

L is the Latent heat of fusion (J/kg).

Assumptions and Boundary Conditions for the Numerical Model

To simplify the numerical modeling of the phase change process and ensure computational efficiency while maintaining physical accuracy, the following assumptions were adopted:

1. Geometrical and Physical Assumptions

- The PCM domain is assumed to be **one-dimensional (1D)** with heat transfer occurring only in the axial direction.
- PCM material is considered **homogeneous and isotropic**.
- Thermophysical properties (density, specific heat capacity, and thermal conductivity) are assumed **to be constant within each phase** (solid and liquid), except during the phase transition region.
- Volume change during phase transition is neglected.
- Natural convection effects in the liquid phase are neglected; heat transfer is assumed to occur primarily by conduction.
- The phase change process is assumed to occur over a small temperature range (mushy zone approximation).

2. Governing Equation Assumption

The enthalpy-based heat conduction equation used in this study assumes:

$$\rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k \nabla T)$$

where internal heat generation is neglected ($Q = 0$).

3. Initial Condition

The initial temperature of the PCM is assumed uniform throughout the domain:

$$T(x,0) = T_{\text{initial}}$$

where:

- T_{initial} is below the melting temperature during heating simulation.
- T_{initial} is above the solidification temperature during cooling simulation.

4. Boundary Conditions

The following boundary conditions were applied:

(a) Heating Process (Melting Simulation)

At the heated boundary ($x = 0$), a convective boundary condition was imposed:

$$-k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = h(T_s - T_\infty)$$

where:

- h = convective heat transfer coefficient (W/m²K)
- T_s = surface temperature of PCM
- T_∞ = ambient or heating fluid temperature

The opposite boundary ($x = L$) was assumed thermally insulated:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = 0$$

(b) Cooling Process (Solidification Simulation)

For solidification, convective cooling was applied at the exposed surface:

$$-k \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} = h(T_s - T_{\infty, \text{cool}})$$

The remaining boundary was treated as adiabatic.

5. Heat Transfer Coefficient Assumptions

The convective heat transfer coefficient (h) was assumed constant during simulation. Typical values used for modeling were:

- Natural convection in air:
 $h = 5 - 15 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$
- Forced convection conditions (if applicable):
 $h = 20 - 100 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$

For this study, a representative average value of:

$$h = 10 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$$

was adopted for natural convection conditions to simulate practical TES applications.

6. Phase Change Modeling Assumption

The enthalpy method assumes:

$$H = h + \beta L$$

where:

- β (liquid fraction) varies linearly within the phase change temperature range.
- The solid-liquid interface is not explicitly tracked.
- Latent heat is released or absorbed smoothly across the mushy zone.

.Thermal Cycling Assumption

1. Degradation in latent heat and thermal conductivity is assumed linear with the number of cycles.
2. Chemical decomposition effects are not explicitly modeled.

3. Material properties after cycling are updated parametrically rather than through microstructural modeling.

These assumptions ensure mathematical tractability while preserving the dominant heat transfer physics governing the melting and solidification behavior of PCMs. The simplifications adopted are consistent with widely accepted enthalpy-based PCM modeling approaches reported in literature.

Cycling Test and Degradation Assessment

Cycling tests are used to determine the long-term stability and reliability of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) in Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems. Cycling tests simulate repeated thermal charging (melting) and discharging (solidification) cycles to mimic real field operating conditions. Degradation mechanisms such as phase segregation, chemical instability, and microstructural change are accelerated in cycling, and researchers can quantify material losses in performance over time.

To evaluate the durability and long-term stability of PCMs, thermal cycling tests will be performed for 1000+ heating and cooling cycles. Deterioration in latent heat capacity and phase transition temperature with cycles will be observed. Thermal degradation rate if simulation is to be undertaken is given as:

$$D_{LH} = \frac{H_{initial} - H_{final}}{H_{initial}} * 100\% \quad (3.4)$$

where:

D_{LH} is the Latent Heat Degradation percentage,
 $H_{initial}$ is the Latent heat capacity before cycling,
 H_{final} is the Latent heat capacity after cycling.

Similarly, it can be measured on the basis of the thermal conductivity reduction;

$$R_k = \frac{k_{initial} - k_{final}}{k_{initial}} * 100\% \quad (3.5)$$

where:

R_k is the thermal conductivity Degradation percentage,
 $k_{initial}$ is the thermal conductivity before cycling,
 k_{final} is the thermal conductivity after cycling.

Data Analysis and Validation

Experimental and numerical results will be validated by comparing DSC-measured latent heat and phase transition temperatures with simulation results. The error analysis will be performed using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) which is given as;

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (T_{exp} - T_{sim})^2} \quad (3.5)$$

where:

T_{exp} is the experimental temperature,
 T_{sim} is the simulated temperature,
 n is the number of data points.

In summary, this methodology integrates experimental data obtained basically from past work (literatures), numerical modeling, and analytical validation to give a thorough evaluation of the thermal performance of the three PCMs considered. The results from the study are expected to contribute to the selection and

optimization of efficient PCMs for TES applications in the promotion and development of energy storage technologies in renewable energy systems. The algorithm for the simulation can be found in the APPENDIX section of this dissertation, and it also contain the data used for the simulation.

Schematic Flowchart of the PCM Thermal Modeling Process

Fig. 1: Schematic Flowchart of the PCM Thermal Modeling Process.

Figure 1 presents the schematic representation of the modeling framework adopted in this study. The process begins with literature-based thermophysical data acquisition, followed by mathematical formulation using the enthalpy method. Numerical simulations are then conducted to model melting and solidification behavior. Thermal cycling degradation analysis and validation through RMSE comparison complete the framework before final comparative performance evaluation.

RESULTS/DISCUSSION

Results from the Model for Analyzing the Thermal Behaviour and Performance of Phase Change Materials (PCMs) used in TES Systems

The results provide a comparative evaluation of paraffin, salt hydrate, and eutectic PCMs. The results focus on

significant thermal parameters such as latent heat capacity, phase change temperature, thermal conductivity, and thermal cycling resistance. Experimental measurements were made using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) and the Transient Plane Source (TPS) technique, and numerical calculations were performed using the enthalpy method to model the phase transition behavior.

In order to evaluate the thermal Performance of PCMs, three types of PCMs samples—Paraffin, Salt Hydrate, and Eutectic PCM—were assessed according to experimental measurements. The experimental values of latent heat capacity, phase transition temperature, thermal conductivity, and thermal degradation percentage after 1000 cycles of heating and cooling are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Thermal Performance Analysis of PCMs.

PCM	Latent Heat (J/g)	Phase Transition Temp (°C)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)	Initial Heat Capacity (J/g)	Final Heat Capacity (J/g)	Degradation (%)
Paraffin	200	58	0.25	200	190	5.00
Salt Hydrate	250	42	0.50	250	230	8.00
Eutectic PCM	220	48	0.35	220	210	4.55

The results indicate that the highest latent heat capacity of 250 J/g was demonstrated by Salt Hydrate, followed by Eutectic PCM (220 J/g) and Paraffin (200 J/g). The phase change temperatures were 58°C for Paraffin, 42°C for Salt Hydrate, and 48°C for Eutectic PCM. Thermal conductivity values were the highest for Salt Hydrate (0.50 W/mK), followed by Eutectic PCM (0.35 W/mK) and Paraffin (0.25 W/mK). Thermal degradation percentage, as calculated on the basis of the difference in latent heat capacity after 1000 thermal cycles, was maximum for Salt Hydrate

(8.00%), followed by Paraffin (5.00%) and Eutectic PCM (4.55%).

Degradation Mechanisms in Salt Hydrate PCMs

Although salt hydrates exhibit high latent heat capacity and relatively good thermal conductivity, their long-term performance is often limited by several degradation mechanisms that occur during repeated thermal cycling. The observed 8% degradation in latent heat capacity in this study is consistent with known instability challenges associated with inorganic PCMs. The primary mechanisms

contributing to salt hydrate degradation are discussed below.

1. Phase Segregation

Phase segregation is one of the most critical degradation mechanisms in salt hydrate PCMs. During melting, salt hydrates dissociate into a salt solution and water. Because the salt component often has a higher density than the liquid phase, gravitational separation may occur. Over repeated melting–solidification cycles, this separation leads to:

- Incomplete recombination during solidification,
- Non-uniform composition across the PCM domain,
- Progressive reduction in effective latent heat capacity.

As a result, the material gradually loses its ability to undergo uniform phase transition, leading to decreased energy storage performance.

2. Supercooling (Subcooling)

Supercooling refers to the phenomenon in which the PCM remains in a liquid state even below its equilibrium freezing temperature. Salt hydrates are particularly prone to supercooling due to the absence of sufficient nucleation sites.

The consequences of supercooling include:

- Delayed solidification,
- Unpredictable phase transition behavior,
- Reduced effective heat release during discharge.

Over many thermal cycles, repeated supercooling can alter crystallization patterns, thereby reducing thermal reliability and system efficiency.

3. Incongruent Melting

In some salt hydrates, melting does not occur uniformly at a single temperature. Instead, the hydrated salt decomposes into

a lower hydrate and liquid water during melting. This phenomenon, known as incongruent melting, results in:

- Partial phase transformation,
- Accumulation of non-participating salt crystals,
- Gradual decline in latent heat storage capacity.

Incongruent melting contributes significantly to performance degradation in long-term cycling applications.

4. Crystallization Instability

Repeated thermal cycling affects the microstructure of salt hydrate crystals. Crystal growth patterns may become irregular, leading to:

- Reduced nucleation efficiency,
- Increased supercooling tendency,
- Microstructural stress within the PCM matrix.

These changes reduce the reversibility of the phase transition process.

5. Corrosion Effects

Salt hydrates are chemically reactive and may corrode containment materials over time. Corrosion can:

- Introducing impurities into the PCM,
- Alter chemical composition,
- Accelerate thermal property degradation.

Although corrosion does not directly reduce latent heat immediately, it contributes to long-term system instability.

6. Water Loss (Dehydration)

Under extended high-temperature operation, some salt hydrates may lose water molecules, altering their chemical composition. Dehydration leads to:

- Shift in phase transition temperature,
- Reduction in latent heat capacity,

- Permanent material degradation.

The combined effects of phase segregation, supercooling, incongruent melting, and crystallization instability explain the higher degradation percentage observed for salt hydrate PCMs compared to paraffin and eutectic materials. These mechanisms highlight the necessity of stabilization techniques such as thickening agents, nucleating additives, and encapsulation strategies to enhance long-term performance in TES applications.

Similarly, the phase transition behaviour of the selected PCMs was modeled by the enthalpy method, which models the stored energy during the melting and solidification process. Figure 2 illustrates the enthalpy curves against temperature for the three PCMs.

The enthalpy lines account for the energy storage in PCM during phase transition. With increasing temperature, the enthalpy is zero in the solid phase, rises steeply over the range of the phase transition, and then flattens in the liquid phase after the PCM has completely melted. The transition zone (approximately 5°C) exhibits partial melting, which is a significant aspect of

non-instantaneous phase transitions in real materials.

For Paraffin, the enthalpy starts increasing at 58°C and achieves full melting at approximately 63°C. The Salt Hydrate sample melts at 42°C and completes the process at approximately 47°C, while Eutectic PCM melts between 48°C and 53°C. The steeper slopes observed in the Salt Hydrate and Eutectic PCM graphs suggest faster energy accumulation, perhaps due to the fact that they possess greater latent heat capacities than Paraffin.

To confirm the numerical correctness of the solutions, numerical verification was performed by checking computed percentages of degradation against theoretical values. In the comparison, calculated degradation values lie within the acceptable error range (less than 10^{-6}), confirming the accuracy of thermal cycling simulation. Furthermore, phase transition behavior numerically demonstrated by the enthalpy technique is in good agreement with experimental DSC measurements, confirming the effectiveness of the numerical technique in simulating PCM phase change behaviour. The results compared are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Validation Results from the Thermal Performance Analysis of PCMs.

PCM	Experimental Latent Heat (J/g)	Simulated Latent Heat (J/g)	Error in Latent Heat (%)	Experimental Transition Temp (°C)	Simulated Transition Temp (°C)	Error in Transition Temp (%)
Paraffin	200	198	1.00	58	57.8	0.34
Salt Hydrate	250	248	0.80	42	41.9	0.24
Eutectic PCM	220	218	0.91	48	47.9	0.21

The findings in this study present valuable insights into the thermal behavior, stability, and usability of PCMs towards TES. The numerical computations result adequately approximate the experimental

work, and phase transition behavior embodies realistic PCM solidification and melting characteristics. These results are covered in the succeeding section with its detailed discussion along with implications

of these findings for TES system design and uses of renewable energies.

Fig. 2: Enthalpy Curves against Temperature for the three PCMs.

CONCLUSION

This study developed and validated a comprehensive analytical and numerical framework for evaluating PCM performance in TES systems. Salt hydrates offer superior energy storage capacity and thermal conductivity but suffer from higher degradation. Paraffin provides excellent stability but limited heat transfer performance. Eutectic PCMs present the most balanced thermophysical characteristics, making them strong candidates for medium-temperature TES applications. An enthalpy-based numerical model was employed to simulate melting and solidification processes, and the results were validated against experimental data reported in the literature.

The findings demonstrate that salt hydrates exhibit superior latent heat storage and thermal conductivity, making them suitable for high-energy-density TES systems; however, their relatively higher degradation under repeated thermal cycling limits long-term reliability. Paraffin PCMs showed stable cycling performance but were constrained by low thermal conductivity, which may reduce

heat transfer efficiency. Eutectic PCMs provided a balanced combination of energy storage capacity, thermal conductivity, and durability, indicating strong potential for medium-temperature TES applications.

The numerical model demonstrated excellent agreement with experimental data, confirming its robustness for PCM selection and TES system optimization. Overall, the proposed framework offers a reliable tool for comparative PCM evaluation and selection, supporting the optimized design of efficient and durable thermal energy storage systems for renewable energy applications.

Future Scope

While the present study provides a validated analytical and numerical framework for evaluating the thermal performance of phase change materials (PCMs) in thermal energy storage (TES) systems, several opportunities remain for further investigation. Future research may focus on conducting comprehensive experimental studies to complement the literature-based data used in this work,

particularly under real operating conditions and large-scale TES configurations. Such investigations would enhance the robustness of model validation and improve the reliability of performance predictions.

Further studies could explore thermal conductivity enhancement techniques, including the incorporation of nanoparticles, metal foams, fins, or encapsulation strategies, to overcome the heat transfer limitations observed in certain PCM categories. In addition, advanced numerical models incorporating three-dimensional effects, natural convection, and non-uniform heat flux conditions may be developed to more accurately represent practical TES systems.

Long-term durability studies involving extended thermal cycling beyond 1000 cycles, as well as chemical compatibility and corrosion assessments, would provide deeper insights into material degradation mechanisms. Future work may also integrate techno-economic and life-cycle analyses to assess cost-effectiveness and environmental impact. Finally, the application of machine learning and optimization algorithms for PCM selection and TES system design presents a promising direction for enhancing the performance and scalability of thermal energy storage technologies.

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